

GREEN ECONOMIC POLICES ROLE IN ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

Khan Shiraz

Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi, India

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***Abstract.** The objective of this study is to introduce and understand the Sustainable Development Goals and concept of a green economy along with related concepts and to evaluate their importance in shaping development policies and addressing socio-economic challenges for the holistic growth. The section dedicated to information and definitions outlines the foundations for the emergence of economic greening as a contemporary developmental phenomenon. It also provides various definitions of green economy, green growth, the principles guiding the implementation of a green economy, and the processes involved in green transformation. The subsequent sections of the study detail the measures and indicators associated with green economy and green growth, highlighting their relationship with the principles and goals of sustainable development. The review of indicators for green economy and green growth includes those developed by specialized United Nations agencies such as UNEP, UNCTAD, the European Union, and the World Bank. The final section of the study examines the concept of Sustainable Development Goals and Role of Green Economic Policies for the attainment of goals. In conclusion, the study aims to present both the potential benefits and challenges associated with prioritizing the greening of the economy, as well as the risks arising from an overreliance on this concept.*

***Keywords:** Sustainable Development Goals, Green Economy, Green Growth, Green Growth Indicators, Green Economy Strategies, Developing Economy.*

1. Introduction

Role of SDG (Sustainable Development Goals): According to the United Nations it is The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development adopted by all the United Nations Member States in 2015, provides a common and shared blueprint for peace

and prosperity for people and the planet, now and into the future. It also seeks to strengthen universal peace in larger freedom. The UN recognizes that eradicating poverty in all its forms and dimensions, including extreme poverty, is the greatest global challenge and an indispensable requirement for sustainable development. All countries and all stakeholders, acting in collaborative partnership, will implement this plan.

The 17 Sustainable Development Goals and 169 aims at achieving ambition of this new universal Agenda. They seek to build on the Millennium Development Goals and complete what these did not achieve. They seek to realize the human rights for all and to achieve gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls globally. They are integrated and indivisible and balance the three dimensions of sustainable development: the economic, social and environmental.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

The Major SDG Goals are as follows:

- 1) No Poverty**
- 2) Zero Hunger**
- 3) Good Health and Well-Being**
- 4) Quality Education**
- 5) Gender Equality**

- 6) **Clean Water and Sanitation**
- 7) **Affordable and Clean Energy**
- 8) **Decent Work and Economic Growth**
- 9) **Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure**
- 10) **Reduced Inequalities**
- 11) **Sustainable Cities and Communities**
- 12) **Responsible Consumption and Production**
- 13) **Climate Action**
- 14) **Life below Water**
- 15) **Life on Land**
- 16) **Peace Justice and Strong Institutions**
- 17) **Partnerships for the Goals**

Green Economic Policies: The term Green Economic Policies involves transitioning to an economic model that emphasizes sustainable and balanced production, exchange, consumption, and distribution of economic and social benefits, with a strong focus on preserving nature and the environment.

One of the most widely quoted definitions of a green economy was proposed by the (UNEP) United Nations Environment Program, which defines green economy as one that results in “increased human well-being and social equity while reducing environmental risks and ecological shortages”.

A green economy refers to an economic framework that seeks to minimize environmental hazards while enhancing social equity and the well-being of individuals. It is structured to operate in harmony with the natural world. Green growth refers to enhancing the potential of environmentally friendly activities and sectors as catalysts for economic expansion. In terms of climate, equal importance is placed on enhancing climate resilience by cutting down on fossil fuel usage and reducing greenhouse gas emissions, which are associated with what is known as low-carbon development. The notion of greening the economy can be described as a shift from the traditional industrial-market development paradigm to one of inclusive development, which is grounded in sustainability and the restoration of ecological balance.

Green Growth:

Green growth focuses on promoting economic development while safeguarding natural resources and environmental services that are essential for our well-being. Achieving this requires stimulating investment and innovation, which will support ongoing growth and create new economic opportunities.

Role of Green Economy and Green Growth in development of Sustainable Development Goals: A key element of the green growth and economic greening concept is its connection to the rapid and extensive transformation processes particularly in developing countries. Transformation is a significant concept that pertains to both economic and social systems, emphasizing their adaptation to environmental standards and sustainable development objectives. Green transformation facilitates the evolution of current systems, including economic frameworks, governance institutions, and the roles of various stakeholders, into innovative alternatives that align with the principles of sustainable development. And thereby enabling to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals

4) Literature Review

Previous studies on economic strategies for sustainable energy have predominantly utilized an economic framework to tackle challenges associated with obtaining clean and affordable energy.

The existing body of literature can be divided into distinct categories based on commonalities in focus and methodology. The first category, which is the most prevalent, investigates how various economic factors influence the attainment of sustainable energy.

This research typically emphasizes specific elements of sustainability, such as the affordability of energy or access to clean energy sources. For example, Legendre and Ricci developed a logistic regression model to explore the relationship between household income and fuel poverty, which is defined as the inability of individuals to adequately heat or cool their homes given their current income levels.

Similarly, Burlinson et al. proposed a model to analyze how income, housing conditions, and energy expenses may impact the extent of fuel poverty . Utilizing

statistical matching techniques.

Romero-Jordán and del Río examined the interactions among various socioeconomic factors, including household income and electricity usage. A significant portion of the research in this category has performed correlation analyses to investigate the connections between energy choices and economic variables, such as the cost of alternative energy sources, household income, and ownership of appliances.

Cheng et al. performed a difference-in-difference analysis to assess the impact of green finance policies on renewable energy adoption across five pilot regions in China. The other area of focus pertains to economic policy uncertainty (EPU), which is characterized by unpredictable regulatory and policy environments in the near term. Research within this domain has explored the relationship between EPU and the advancement of sustainable energy. Yet another finding by Yu et al. states how EPU affects the carbon emission intensity of manufacturing companies, discovering that EPU contributes to a greater reliance on fossil fuels.

Raszka et al. provides an in-depth evaluation of the possibilities for post-industrial growth in urban areas and municipalities, considering social, economic, and environmental factors. The authors aim to identify strategic objectives that, when achieved, will facilitate the acceleration of sustainable development through a multidimensional analysis.

Furthermore, Bakhsh et al. investigated the impact of green finance policies on the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal by directing investments towards renewable energy initiatives in OECD nations. They emphasized the potential of financial incentives to facilitate the shift towards sustainable energy sources. Despite the significant influence of OECD and European countries on global energy consumption and policy formulation, there exists a considerable gap in the literature concerning the policy deficiencies and opportunities within these areas. Most current research tends to concentrate on individual policies, such as green finance programs or environmental regulations, evaluating their effects on the achievement. However, the broader context of energy sustainability which encompasses a diverse range of

interrelated policies has not been adequately examined.

2. Research Methodology

The main research methodology is to measure the progress of "Green" growth by determining the level and quantum of influence of economic and environmental indicators, as a methodological basis for developing mechanisms for maintaining economic well-being relations in the context of sustainable development of the nation.

The methodology is based of the recommendations formed by the convergence of four methodological approaches:

1. Methods of evaluation of the indicators of Green Growth of the OECD; (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. This group consists of the indicators for estimating the amount of resource consumed (resource productivity of GDP). The main ones are water and energy productivity of GDP.

2) The second approach is formed by the indicators for assessing the negative impact on the environment .The main ones are the carbon productivity of GDP and the waste productivity of GDP. The ratio of the Total GDP and the amount of environmental resources utilized signifies the Indicator of Environment Productivity of GDP.

3) The third approach which affects the GDP is the Structural Transformations in the Economy (industrial, construction, agricultural, etc. The quantum of capital investment and current expenditures, and structural changes in environmental investment affects the Green Economy. The GDP and Productivity of the average annual population and the amount of expenditures on Structural Changes in Environmental Investment.

4) The Other Approach which affects the resources and the Economic components is start assessing the parameters of economic security of the state and the dynamics of indicators-factors of influence, since they directly or indirectly also affect the components of all indicators of resource and environmental productivity of GDP in the economy.

2. Analysis and Results

The notion of a green economy is gaining recognition as an essential

mechanism for realizing sustainable development goals (SDGs). This approach focuses on harmonizing economic advancement with environmental sustainability and conservation. The green economy seeks to lower carbon emissions, optimize resource utilization, and foster social inclusivity, thereby closely aligning with the aims of the SDGs.

Various methodological approaches have been utilized in research to assess and prioritize the effectiveness of green economy strategies in relation to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Techniques like the Decision Making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory (DEMATEL) and the Analytic Network Process (ANP) have been employed to assess and rank the most significant variables within the green economy framework. These methodologies facilitate a deeper understanding of the intricate relationships among various sustainability criteria and their impact on the attainment of SDGs.

3. Conclusion/Recommendation:

Green Economic Policies Role in Achieving Sustainable Development Goals

Green finance is essential in facilitating the shift towards a sustainable economy by providing financial support for projects that enhance both environmental and economic sustainability. In countries where it has been implemented, the green finance has significantly contributed to the advancement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by fostering the development of green technologies and supporting micro-enterprises.

The New Green Economic Policies has emerged as a collective aspiration to synchronize the economic ambitions with environmental sustainability. The various dimensions of the “Green Economy,” “Green Growth” “Green Future”. It offers fresh perspective for sustainability and further industrialization and economic growth and stability. Green economy as based on six main sectors

The essential recommendations for enhancing the evaluation of transformations within the green economy. These include:

- Improved indicators of 'progress' that extend beyond GDP;
- Comprehensive evaluation of the interactions between the economy, society

& the environment;

- Enhanced economic metrics for assessing green economy transformations;
- Adoption of alternative measurement strategies, incorporating innovative

methodologies and diverse data sources.

Renewable energy: To what extent the country is switching towards the various types of environmental friendly options. The shift to less carbon-intensive and more sustainable energy systems is centered on renewables, which include solar, wind, hydropower, biofuels, and others. Due to regulatory assistance and significant cost reductions for solar photovoltaics and wind power in particular, generating capacity has increased quickly in recent years. Efforts should be made to encourage the use of Renewable Energy for the cost benefits and sustainability of the environment. Most of the developing economies are now shifting their focus on encouraging Renewable Energy.

Green buildings: Throughout a building's life-cycle, green building—also referred to as green construction, sustainable building, or eco-friendly building—refers to both a structure and the implementation of resource-efficient and environmentally conscious practices: planning, designing, building, operating, maintaining, remodeling, and demolishing. This is comparatively a new concept but has a long lasting impact on the sustainability of the country. With the increase in the Construction and allied activities almost everywhere in the globe there is special need of attention whereby the Nations should adopt in attaining the activities involved around the concepts of Green building.

Sustainable transport: Transportation that is sustainable in terms of its effects on the environment and society is known as sustainable transportation. The specific vehicles utilized for air, sea, or road transportation; the energy source; and the infrastructure (roads, railroads, airways, waterways, canals, and terminals) that supports the transportation are all factors in assessing sustainability. Evaluation also includes transit-oriented development, logistics, and transportation operations. The effectiveness and efficiency of the transportation system, as well as the system's effects on the environment and climate, are key indicators of transportation sustainability.

Transport is the life line of the economy various multimodal transport webbed together prepares an effective green sustainable transport. More and more efforts should be given on using e-vehicles in both private and public transport system. Other less pollution emission options like using battery operated vehicles, CNG (Compressed Natural Gas) or LPG (Liquefied Petroleum Gas) for commercial transportation. Solar power vehicles should also be encouraged with proper research and development in non-biodegradable power sources.

Water management: In general, water management is the planning and allocation for the usage of water resources, which is being done under certain policies and regulations governing the amount of water being used and at what place. The management of: drinking water (water treatment), industrial water, sewage or wastewater is: water resource management, flood protection management, irrigation management, water table management.

Appropriate Water Treatment Plants should be established. With an intention to re-cycle the water with proper filtration for reusing. Rain harvesting is also one of the option to conserve the water cycle and maintaining the ecological water cycle in the atmosphere.

Waste management: Waste management or waste disposal is all those activities and actions required to manage waste from its inception to its final disposal. This encompasses the collection, transport, treatment, and disposal of waste, as well as the supervision and regulation of the waste management process and waste-related laws, technologies, and economic mechanisms.

Proper Segregation and disposal of the waste according to the categories. Now many countries have already started the concept of waste segregation according to the disposal and re-cycle process of the waste. The sustainable way is to process the waste in outskirts of the city with minimum carbon emission and using the bio-waste in making fertilizers and organic manure.

Disposing and handling of waste depends as waste could either be solid, liquid or gases. It handles various types of garbage like industrial, biological, municipal, household, radioactive wastes, organic, biomedical wastes. Waste can even threaten

human health in some cases. Health problems are related to almost all aspects of waste management. Directly through the management of solid waste, and indirectly through health issues may also arise:

Land management: It is the process through which the controlling how land resources are used and developed is known. It includes Agriculture, Forestry, Water Resources, Human Settlements and Tourism. The land is limited and every utility has to be managed in that only. Those activities which eventually pollutes the land should be minimized. With proper development and plantation drives the green area can be increased which will be beneficial for the environment and also soil erosion can be minimized. There is also a need by the respective concerned department to ensure that no illegal or unauthorized use of land takes place. Saving and conserving land deterioration is one goal of land management.

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